

SUSTAINABLE SOCIAL COMMERCE SYSTEM

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Background

Organization and Business Domain

The world is faces massive environmental problems, many of which occur due to human activities. The number of environmental problems is growing day by day. Meanwhile, mobile phones have become an integral part of everyone's lives, and their use allows users to interact with calls and innovative and advanced applications. Mobile applications, web pages, and Facebook pages have been introduced in Sri Lanka to share knowledge and inspire people about waste management and eco-friendly activities.

Overview of the Existing System

How the existing system functions:

Currently, people use mobile apps to provide solutions to waste, enhance people's awareness about the environment, and provide updates related to the environment. These apps have community platforms, provide daily news about the environment, create environmental events, provide sound pollution detectors, and give a tracker to track users' activities and challenges.

Problems with the existing System:

Current environment-related apps do not provide a proper solution for making awareness about environmental issues and are not very user-friendly. A few buying and selling platforms are available for eco-friendly products, and well-known e-commerce sites do not prioritise these products. There are numerous applications available that present users with environmental challenges. However, users are only weakly motivated to use these applications.

System Analysis

Problem Analysis

Due to human activities, major environmental issues are arising now. After observing the society, we have identified that most of these problems occur due to the lack of social awareness. Environmentalists and social activists are trying to increase awareness of these problems and find solutions collectively, but there are no dedicated platforms to do so. In addition, people who care about the environment are showing an interest to buy eco-friendly products. Environment-related challenges are one of the popular ways to influence people to be eco-friendly. Notwithstanding, there is no such excellent user-oriented platform to give these challenges a worthy reward for their completion, change their lifestyle, and make them eco-friendly.

Requirement Analysis

The following functional requirements were identified based on the main modules of the system.

Module/Actor	User	Administrator
Social Community Platform Module	Create a profile, Log in, Reset Password, Edit profile, Logout, Send friend requests, Accept or reject friend requests, Search friends, Share posts and stories, Chat with other users, Create groups, Report Content, Create pages, Likes, comments and share	Update content, Validate user login, Respond to the user's request, Block unnecessary contents
Eco-Shopping Module	Search for products, Rate products, Provide feedback, Check payment history,	Overall Controlling

	Request to buy the product, Make payments, Add new products, Remove previously added products, Create a Business Account, Change product details	
Eco-Challenge Module	View challenges, Accept challenges, View challenge history, Likes and comments, Share challenges, Create new challenges, Check participants' responses	Remove unnecessary challenges
Daily Motivational Quote – Notification Module	View notifications, Delete notifications, Check notification history	Add quotes

System Development

Development Methodology used:

As the development methodology, the Waterfall Method was used, and the team followed the stages of the Software Development Life Cycle.

Technologies used:

Visual Studio Code was used as the development environment, and MySQL was used as the DBMS. HTML, CSS, JavaScript, and PHP languages were used to develop this system. Laravel was used as the back-end framework.

Conclusion

This system provides a platform to raise awareness about environmental problems and motivate people to be eco-friendly using social media features, an e-commerce platform, motivational quotes, and interactive challenges. Developers are planning to improve the system using React Native and Non-relational databases.

References

<https://theecohub.com/sustainability-apps/>